

Towards the Creation of a Network of Strategic Joint University–Industry Laboratories: A Design-Oriented Case Study

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Abstract

University–industry collaboration represents a persistent challenge in contexts characterized by fragmented innovation systems and a strong presence of small and medium-sized enterprises. Although mission-oriented innovation policies increasingly promote the creation of joint laboratories and collaborative infrastructures, transforming pilot initiatives into stable and continuous partnerships is frequently complex. This paper presents an exploratory and design-oriented case study concerning the digital platform developed within Cross-Cutting Activity #2 (CC2) of the iNEST (Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem) consortium.

Instead of evaluating collaboration outcomes, the analysis focuses on the design rationale, architecture, and early implementation stages of a digital platform conceived to enable future university–industry collaborations. The platform is interpreted as a digital boundary object aimed at increasing the visibility of researchers, laboratories, and expertise, while supporting matchmaking activities, online co-working, and the collaborative development of research and innovation projects.

Based on early pilot experiences and initial experimental uses, the work discusses the opportunities and structural constraints of platform-based approaches for ecosystem orchestration. The results highlight how digital infrastructures can reduce discovery and coordination costs, while emphasizing the crucial role of organizational readiness and sustained engagement for their effective adoption. This contribution enriches the literature on digital platforms and innovation ecosystems by offering design insights to facilitate, as opposed to merely presupposing, university–industry collaboration in early-stage mission-driven initiatives.

Keywords

Innovation Ecosystems, University–Business, Lab Village, Joint Laboratories, Technology Transfer, Digital Platforms, iNEST, PNRR

1. Introduction: Context and research focus

1.1 The iNEST ecosystem: institutional context and mandate

The iNEST project (Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem) is a large-scale innovation initiative funded under Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), within Mission 4, Component 2. Conceived as a mission-oriented intervention, iNEST aims to strengthen research and innovation capacities in the North-Eastern regions of Italy (Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, and

53 the Autonomous Provinces of Trento and Bolzano), with a specific focus on the digital
 54 transformation of key industrial sectors. Existing literature highlights how the effectiveness of public
 55 funding programs is strongly shaped by policy design choices and institutional contexts (Dimos &
 56 Pugh, 2016), particularly in regions characterized by industrial fragmentation and a predominance
 57 of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

58
 59 The iNEST ecosystem is organized according to a Hub & Spoke governance model. The Hub,
 60 coordinated by the University of Padua, is responsible for overall management, strategic
 61 coordination, monitoring, and interaction with the Ministry of Universities and Research (MUR).
 62 This governance structure is part of a broader national trend in Italy, where the mandatory adoption
 63 of the Hub & Spoke model for PNRR-funded ecosystems aims to standardize university-industry
 64 engagement and knowledge transfer dynamics (Compagnucci et al., 2025). The operational core
 65 of the ecosystem consists of nine Spokes, each led by a regional university and focused on a
 66 specific thematic domain aligned with regional specialization patterns (figure 1). This organizational
 67 architecture reflects broader European policy orientations, including the vision of the European
 68 Research Area, which emphasizes excellence, openness, and competitiveness through
 69 coordinated and network-based research infrastructures (European Commission, 2020).

70
 71 In line with mission-oriented innovation policies (Mazzucato, 2018), iNEST does not primarily target
 72 isolated technological outputs, but rather seeks to foster conditions conducive to long-term
 73 knowledge transfer and collaborative innovation across institutional and territorial boundaries. The
 74 underlying assumption is that addressing structural gaps between academic research and the local
 75 productive system requires not only investments in research infrastructure, but also the
 76 development of organizational and relational mechanisms capable of supporting sustained
 77 interaction among heterogeneous actors within a supra-regional innovation ecosystem (Asheim &
 78 Isaksen, 2002; Camagni, 2002; Acs et al., 2018).

79 **Figure 1.** Structure of the iNEST Consortium Spokes

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 81 **1.2 Cross-Cutting Activity #2 as a mission-oriented initiative**

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 83 Within this framework, the iNEST Consortium includes a set of Cross-Cutting Activities (CCs),
 84 conceived as horizontal initiatives operating across all Spokes (figure 2). These activities are
 85 intended to ensure methodological coherence, facilitate knowledge circulation, and explore

86 scalable approaches that can be adapted across different thematic and territorial contexts.
87 Cross-Cutting Activity #2 (CC2), led by the University of Udine, is specifically mandated with
88 addressing the challenge of university–industry collaboration through the conceptualization and
89 exploration of new organizational and infrastructural models.
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91
92 **Figure 2.** The iNEST Cross Cutting Activities
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94 CC2 is framed as a transversal, mission-oriented initiative inspired by the Triple Helix model
95 (Etzkowitz, 2008), which emphasizes the dynamic interaction among universities, industry, and
96 public institutions as a key driver of innovation. Rather than focusing on short-term technology
97 transfer outcomes, CC2 aims to investigate how more structured and durable forms of
98 collaboration could be enabled between academic laboratories and firms, particularly in contexts
99 characterized by institutional fragmentation and limited absorptive capacity.

100

101 The long-term vision articulated within CC2 is the progressive development of a network of so-
102 called Lab Villages, conceived as joint university-industry environments that combine physical,
103 organizational, and digital dimensions. As exemplified by the Lab Village in Udine (Figure 3), these
104 environments are characterized by a modular physical architecture where distinct research units
105 are co-located to facilitate spontaneous and structured interactions. However, this study does not
106 assume the existence of such a network as an accomplished outcome. Instead, it focuses on the
107 early-stage design choices, organizational assumptions, and enabling mechanisms that underpin
108 this vision. In this sense, CC2 is treated as an exploratory initiative aimed at testing concepts,
109 formats, and tools that may contribute, over time, to the emergence of more stable collaborative
110 configurations.

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Figure 3. The modular architecture of the Lab Village in Udine. The different colors and distinct labeling of each module reflect the multi-disciplinary nature of the joint laboratories.

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Among the key components envisioned within CC2 is the design of a digital platform intended to support visibility, matchmaking, and early forms of distributed collaboration among researchers, laboratories, and firms. This platform is conceived not as a standalone solution, but as a coordinating device whose effectiveness depends on future adoption, integration with local practices, and alignment with broader governance arrangements within the ecosystem.

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1.3 The Lab Village concept as a design hypothesis

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The Lab Village concept represents the central design hypothesis underlying CC2. Instead of being treated as a fully established organizational model, the Lab Village is conceptualized as an exploratory construct aimed at rethinking how joint university–industry laboratories can function as interface infrastructures within complex innovation ecosystems. Its theoretical foundations were initially articulated in Deliverable DCC2.1 (iNEST–CC2, 2023), which examined the evolution of joint laboratories toward more integrated models of co-innovation and academic entrepreneurship (Perkmann & Walsh, 2007; Meissner et al., 2022).

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In this perspective, a Lab Village can be defined as a physical, digital, or hybrid environment in which academic and industrial actors are expected to collaborate around shared research and innovation challenges. The Lab Village is interpreted as a boundary object (Star & Griesemer, 1989): a socio-technical construct that maintains a coherent identity across different institutional domains, while remaining flexible enough to accommodate heterogeneous goals, practices, and constraints. Its defining ambition lies in enabling processes of co-creation and in supporting the joint exploration of scientific and technological trajectories, as opposed to focusing on the delivering predefined outputs.

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From an organizational standpoint, the Lab Village can be understood as a device for fostering the gradual development of shared capabilities between universities and firms. Such capabilities are assumed to emerge over time through repeated interactions, learning processes, and the alignment of routines and expectations (Dosi, Nelson, & Winter, 2000). This approach departs from traditional, transaction-oriented models of technology transfer, which often struggle with cultural misalignment, limited time horizons, and weak relational embeddedness (Siegel et al., 2003; Rossoni, 2023).

149

150 A key challenge identified in the early phases of CC2 concerns the translation of the Lab Village
151 concept into operational configurations that can be meaningfully adapted across heterogeneous
152 institutional and territorial contexts. Far from proposing a standardized blueprint, CC2 has explored
153 the Lab Village as a flexible design space, within which different pilot experiences and experimental
154 formats can be used to investigate the conditions under which more stable and strategic forms of
155 university–industry collaboration might eventually emerge.

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157 **1.4 Theoretical framework: Lab Villages, open innovation, and enabling infrastructures**

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159 The conceptualization of the Lab Village within the iNEST ecosystem is grounded in established
160 theoretical perspectives on innovation dynamics, knowledge transfer, and the organization of
161 collaborative research. Far from being interpreted as a purely infrastructural intervention, the Lab
162 Village is framed as a socio-technical construct situated at the intersection of organizational
163 theory, innovation studies, and regional development. This section outlines the main theoretical
164 lenses informing the analysis, with particular attention to the role of interface structures, boundary
165 objects, and coordination mechanisms in university–industry collaboration (Asheim & Isaksen,
166 2002).

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168 **1.4.1 Triple Helix interactions and the role of the entrepreneurial university**

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170 The overall orientation of iNEST and the mandate of CC2 are informed by the Triple Helix
171 framework, which conceptualizes innovation as the outcome of dynamic interactions among
172 universities, industry, and government actors (Etzkowitz, 2008). Within this perspective,
173 universities are no longer seen solely as producers of scientific knowledge, but as active
174 participants in innovation ecosystems, engaging in collaborative arrangements that extend
175 beyond traditional technology transfer channels.

176

177 In this context, the Lab Village can be interpreted as a design hypothesis aligned with the notion
178 of the entrepreneurial university. Instead of assuming a direct or automatic contribution to
179 economic development, the Lab Village provides a conceptual space in which universities
180 experiment with new organizational roles, interfaces, and collaborative practices aimed at
181 facilitating interaction with industry (Meissner et al., 2022). The Hub & Spoke architecture adopted
182 by iNEST offers a macro-regional governance framework within which such experimentation can
183 take place, while leaving room for local adaptation and institutional diversity (iNEST, 2022).

184

185 **1.4.2 Open innovation, knowledge flows, and boundary objects**

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187 The Lab Village concept is further informed by the open innovation paradigm, which emphasizes
188 the permeability of organizational boundaries and the bidirectional circulation of knowledge
189 between internal and external actors (Chesbrough, 2003). From this perspective, effective
190 university–industry collaboration depends not only on the availability of technological outputs, but
191 also on the capacity to integrate heterogeneous forms of knowledge, including industrial
192 problems, data, constraints, and application contexts.

193

194 Within CC2, the Lab Village is conceived as an interface that could support such bidirectional
195 knowledge flows, moving beyond linear “technology push” models of transfer. In particular, the
196 Lab Village is interpreted as a boundary object (Star & Griesemer, 1989): a structure that enables
197 coordination across institutional domains by providing shared reference points, while remaining
198 sufficiently flexible to accommodate divergent goals and practices. Prior research highlights how
199 boundary objects play a critical role in matchmaking processes and in reducing communication

200 barriers between scientific and industrial communities (Caccamo et al., 2023).
 201 As depicted in Figure 4, the Lab Village acts as this central interface, mapping the complex
 202 interactions and knowledge flows between academia and the industrial sector, thus
 203 operationalizing the open innovation paradigm within a structured regional ecosystem.

204 **Figure 4.** Lab Village ecosystem: actors and interactions.
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 208 **1.4.3 Joint laboratories as interface and coordination structures**

209
 210 The Lab Village builds conceptually on the literature on university–industry joint laboratories,
 211 which are typically described as hybrid organizational arrangements combining academic and
 212 industrial resources around shared research agendas (Perkmann & Walsh, 2007; Fraser & Mancl,
 213 2021). Existing studies emphasize that the effectiveness of joint labs depends less on their formal
 214 structure than on their ability to manage persistent tensions between academic and commercial
 215 logics, time horizons, and incentive systems (Meissner et al., 2022).

216
 217 In this sense, the Lab Village is not treated as a standardized or fully realized organizational
 218 model, but as a potential interface structure whose role is to support coordination, capability
 219 building, and repeated interaction over time. The ambition articulated within CC2, namely, the
 220 progressive connection of multiple joint laboratories into broader collaborative configurations, can
 221 therefore be understood as an exploratory response to territorial fragmentation and institutional
 222 heterogeneity, as opposed to an accomplished transformation. From a theoretical standpoint, this
 223 positions the Lab Village as an enabling infrastructure whose contribution to ecosystem-level
 224 collaboration depends on governance arrangements, organizational readiness, and sustained
 225 engagement, rather than on infrastructural presence alone (Tödtling & Trippel, 2005).

2. Mapping and exploratory analysis of initial conditions

2.1 Activity planning and exploratory research design

The initial phase of Cross-Cutting Activity #2 (CC2), concluded with Milestone 17 (April 2023), was primarily dedicated to activity planning and to the exploratory analysis of existing university–industry collaboration practices across the iNEST Spokes. The phase shunned the assumption of homogeneous starting conditions, acting instead as a mapping exercise aimed at understanding the diversity of organizational arrangements, collaboration formats, and institutional configurations already present within the ecosystem.

Table 1 Milestones of CC2 Activity

Task	Main Objective	Reference phase
CC2.1	Synthesis of the activity plan	M17
CC2.2	Consolidation and expansion of existing labs and settlement of new labs	M18
CC2.3	Pilot experiences, and knowledge and technology transfer initiatives	M19
CC2.3	Definition of models of Lab Village and development of a digital platform	M20

The CC2 activity plan was articulated into a sequence of tasks corresponding to different analytical and experimental phases (Table 1). These tasks were designed to progressively move from conceptual framing and landscape analysis (M17 and M18), to the exploration of pilot formats and early collaborative experiences (M19), and finally to the design of enabling tools, including a digital platform intended to support visibility and coordination (M20). In this sense, the milestones should be interpreted as stages in an exploratory and iterative process; they are not linear steps toward predefined outcomes.

Deliverable DCC2.1 provided a structured overview of the initial conditions of the ecosystem, offering a shared knowledge base to inform subsequent design choices. Its purpose was not to evaluate performance, but to support collective learning and to identify recurring patterns, constraints, and opportunities relevant to the development of future collaborative infrastructures.

2.2 Mapping the initial landscape of university–industry collaboration

The core of the M17 deliverable consisted of a systematic mapping of existing university initiatives across all nine iNEST Spokes (Universities of Bolzano, Trento, Udine, IUAV, Padua, Ca' Foscari Venice, Verona, Trieste, and SISSA). The mapping exercise extended beyond a simple inventory of physical laboratories, encompassing organizational, relational, and operational dimensions of university–industry collaboration.

Specifically, the analysis considered aspects such as governance arrangements, funding mechanisms, duration of partnerships, and types of outputs. This approach made it possible to capture the heterogeneity of collaboration practices across institutions and territories, highlighting

266 differences in organizational structures, degrees of formalization, and strategic orientation. The
267 results of the mapping revealed a broad spectrum of configurations, ranging from more structured
268 joint initiatives to looser, project-based or service-oriented forms of interaction.

269
270 Rather than interpreting this heterogeneity in normative terms, the analysis treated it as an
271 empirical feature of the ecosystem. The diversity of initial conditions underscored the need for
272 flexible and adaptive approaches to collaboration, capable of accommodating different
273 institutional histories, capacities, and strategic priorities.

274 275 **2.3 Typologies of collaboration and initial configurations**

276
277 Building on the mapping exercise, Deliverable M18 proposed an analytical classification of the
278 observed collaboration practices, with the aim of supporting comparative analysis and informing
279 the design of pilot experiences. Instead of hierarchical “maturity levels,” this classification
280 identified a set of ideal-typical configurations reflecting different ways in which university–industry
281 collaboration was organized at the outset of CC2.

282
283 A first configuration included contexts in which no dedicated structures or formalized initiatives
284 related to joint laboratories were present. In these cases, collaboration activities, where they
285 existed, were typically episodic and project-based, relying on informal networks or individual
286 relationships.

287
288 A second configuration encompassed laboratories and competence centers engaged in
289 interactions with firms, but lacking some of the elements commonly associated with long-term
290 joint laboratories, such as shared strategic roadmaps, stable organizational arrangements, or
291 sustained corporate presence. These configurations reflected intermediate forms of collaboration,
292 often shaped by short-term funding schemes or service-oriented logics.

293
294 A third configuration consisted of more structured joint initiatives that predated iNEST,
295 characterized by formal agreements, shared infrastructures, and longer-term collaborative
296 trajectories. These experiences provided valuable insights into both the potential and the
297 challenges of sustaining university–industry partnerships over time.

298
299 Importantly, these configurations should be understood as analytical lenses, not developmental
300 stages. They capture diversity in organizational forms instead of linear progression, and they
301 informed the subsequent design of pilot activities and enabling tools by highlighting different
302 needs, constraints, and opportunities across the ecosystem.

303 304 **2.4 Implications for pilot activities and platform design**

305
306 The exploratory mapping and classification of initial conditions played a key role in shaping the
307 subsequent phases of CC2. The heterogeneity of collaboration configurations suggested that a
308 one-size-fits-all approach to the development of Lab Villages would be neither feasible nor
309 desirable. Instead, CC2 adopted an experimental logic, using pilot experiences and temporary
310 collaborative formats to explore how different organizational settings might engage with the Lab
311 Village concept.

312
313 At the same time, the mapping exercise highlighted the relevance of shared infrastructural tools
314 capable of supporting visibility, coordination, and early interaction across institutional boundaries.
315 In this context, the design of a digital platform emerged as a response to the observed
316 fragmentation of information and practices, with the aim of providing a common interface
317 adaptable to diverse collaboration configurations. These insights informed the platform’s design
318 as an enabling infrastructure, rather than as a prescriptive solution, consistent with the exploratory

319 and design-oriented orientation of the study.

320

321 **3. From exploratory analysis to design requirements**

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323 **3.1 From internal monitoring to analytical interpretation**

324

325 Following the exploratory mapping phase (M17), Cross-Cutting Activity #2 (CC2) entered a phase
326 of internal reflection aimed at interpreting the diversity of organizational configurations observed
327 across the iNEST ecosystem. Milestone 18 (M18) was originally conceived as an internal
328 monitoring exercise to support coordination and planning within the consortium. However, for the
329 purposes of this study, the materials produced in this phase are reinterpreted analytically, shifting
330 the focus from assessment to the identification of design-relevant dimensions and structural
331 tensions.

332

333 The outputs of M18 are not treated as quantitative evidence of performance or progress; instead,
334 this paper adopts a qualitative and interpretive perspective. The indicators and comparative
335 observations developed during CC2 activities are used here as heuristic tools to surface recurring
336 challenges, trade-offs, and constraints relevant to the design of enabling infrastructures for
337 university–industry collaboration.

338

339 **3.2 Design-relevant dimensions emerging from CC2 activities**

340

341 The internal analysis conducted during CC2 highlighted a set of recurring dimensions that proved
342 critical in shaping the feasibility and orientation of collaborative laboratory initiatives. These
343 dimensions did not emerge as standardized variables, but as cross-cutting issues encountered
344 across heterogeneous institutional contexts. The main dimensions, along with the observed
345 evidence and their design implications, are summarized in Table 2.

346

347 A first dimension concerns physical and digital infrastructure. While the availability of dedicated
348 spaces was often considered a prerequisite for collaboration, CC2 activities consistently showed
349 that infrastructural readiness alone did not guarantee sustained interaction with industrial
350 partners. This finding resonates with broader literature emphasizing that collaboration depends
351 on organizational and relational factors beyond spatial proximity.

352

353 A second dimension concerns collaboration patterns. The evidence gathered through CC2
354 activities indicates that interactions between laboratories and industrial partners are
355 predominantly episodic and fragmented. Rather than following a structured long-term
356 development path, these collaborations often take the form of one-off consultations or specific
357 problem-solving interventions. This pattern suggests that physical proximity is insufficient to
358 trigger spontaneous synergy; consequently, additional relational and coordination mechanisms
359 are required to transform these isolated episodes into a continuous collaborative flow.

360

361 A third dimension relates to governance and coordination mechanisms. The analysis revealed a
362 significant 'governance gap': in contexts where Lab Villages are still in an embryonic stage, formal
363 coordination is obviously absent. However, even in more structured environments like Udine or
364 Bolzano, a unified governance model is often missing. This is due to the departmental nature of
365 the laboratories, which remain independent and autonomous entities even when co-located.
366 These laboratories answer to different departmental hierarchies and scientific missions, making
367 the Lab Village a physical cluster of autonomous units rather than an integrated organizational
368 body. This structural independence creates a trade-off between the flexibility of individual
369 research groups and the strategic stability needed for ecosystem-level engagement.

370

371 A fourth dimension involves the temporal horizon of collaboration. Many initiatives were
 372 characterized by short-term, project-based interactions, often driven by external funding cycles.
 373 The absence of shared roadmaps or long-term commitments emerged as a recurrent constraint
 374 to deeper forms of co-creation.

375
 376 Finally, the analysis addressed the role of digital support. Currently, the digital landscape within
 377 the ecosystem is highly fragmented, with information about competencies, equipment, and
 378 research outputs scattered across different university portals or departmental websites. This lack
 379 of a unified digital interface increases 'discovery costs' for companies and hinders cross-spoke
 380 interaction. The design implication is the necessity of a shared enabling platform that acts as a
 381 single point of entry, providing the visibility and coordination tools needed to support the entire
 382 lifecycle of university-industry projects.

383
 384 **Table 2 – Design-relevant dimensions emerging from CC2 activities**

Observed dimension	Recurring evidence	Design implications
Infrastructure	Dedicated spaces are present but uneven across contexts	Physical infrastructure alone does not ensure sustained collaboration
Collaboration patterns	Interactions are predominantly episodic and one-off.	Additional relational and coordination mechanisms are required
Governance arrangements	Structural Fragmentation: Labs are departmental, independent, and autonomous, even when physically co-located (e.g., Udine, Bolzano).	The digital platform must act as a lightweight orchestrator, enabling collaboration without infringing on the autonomy of individual labs.
Temporal orientation	Short-term horizons prevail	Long-term co-creation is structurally constrained
Digital support	Digital solutions and information sources are fragmented.	A shared enabling platform can support coordination and visibility

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 386

387 **3.3 Structural tensions in Lab Village design**

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 389 The dimensions identified above can be interpreted as manifestations of broader structural
 390 tensions inherent in the design of collaborative research infrastructures. One such tension
 391 concerns the balance between infrastructural investment and relational engagement: while
 392 physical and digital assets are necessary enablers, they are insufficient in the absence of
 393 mechanisms supporting trust-building, repeated interaction, and mutual learning.

394
 395 A second tension reflects the classic dilemma between exploration and exploitation. University–
 396 industry laboratories are expected to support scientific experimentation while simultaneously
 397 delivering industrially relevant outcomes. Managing this tension requires organizational
 398 arrangements capable of accommodating divergent time horizons and incentive structures,
 399 echoing the literature on organizational ambidexterity (O'Reilly & Tushman, 2013).

400
 401 A further tension emerges between standardization and contextual adaptation. While the ambition
 402 of CC2 was to promote shared models and interoperability across the ecosystem, the diversity of
 403 institutional settings and sectoral domains suggested that overly rigid frameworks could
 404 undermine local engagement. This issue is particularly salient in sectors such as cultural and
 405 creative industries, where collaboration practices are less formalized and require context-
 406 sensitive indicators and engagement formats (Bruzzi & Busacca, 2024).

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 408

409 **3.4 Pilot experiences as design probes**

410
 411 In response to these tensions, CC2 adopted pilot experiences as an exploratory design strategy;
 412 the focus was not on immediate scaling or evaluation, but on using these initiatives as design

413 probes: bounded, context-specific initiatives aimed at testing assumptions, exploring
414 organizational configurations, and generating actionable insights for the refinement of the Lab
415 Village concept.

416

417 These pilots were not conceived as representative or generalizable solutions, but as opportunities
418 to observe how different dimensions—governance, infrastructure, digital tools, and engagement
419 practices—interacted in practice. The insights generated through these experiments informed
420 both the conceptual development of the Lab Village model and the design of a digital platform
421 intended to support visibility, matchmaking, and early-stage collaboration (Biason, 2025a).

422

423 **3.5 Illustrative design probes from CC2**

424

425 To illustrate how pilot experiences informed design choices, this section briefly discusses three
426 cases selected for their diversity in institutional context and strategic orientation.

427

- 428 • **Spoke 3 (University of Udine): Contamination Lab**

429

430 The Contamination Lab developed within Spoke 3 represents an experimental environment
431 combining physical space, methodological frameworks, and facilitated interaction among
432 students, researchers, and external stakeholders. Moving beyond the functions of a traditional
433 laboratory, the initiative emphasized cross-disciplinary collaboration and problem framing.
434 The materials produced during this pilot (Biason, 2025b) contributed to clarifying governance
435 requirements and engagement rules relevant to early-stage university–industry interaction.

436

- 437 • **Spoke 9 (SISSA and University of Trieste): Advanced Research Contexts**

438

439 The pilot activities conducted within Spoke 9 focused on advanced research domains such
440 as artificial intelligence and data science, where collaboration with industry raises specific
441 challenges related to data access, confidentiality, and intellectual property. The
442 documentation of these experiences (Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati &
443 University of Trieste, 2025) provided insights into how boundary conditions can be negotiated
444 without compromising academic autonomy, highlighting the importance of flexible interface
445 structures.

446

- 447 • **Spoke 1 (Free University of Bozen-Bolzano): Digital representations of laboratories**

448

449 The pilot developed at the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano explored the use of digital tools
450 to increase accessibility and visibility of laboratory infrastructures through virtual
451 representations. This approach addressed spatial and logistical barriers faced by small and
452 medium-sized enterprises, offering design insights for hybrid physical–digital collaboration
453 models. These insights directly informed the requirements of the Lab Village digital platform.

454

455 **3.6 Implications for platform-oriented enabling infrastructures**

456

457 Taken together, the exploratory analysis and pilot experiences suggest that the main contribution
458 of CC2 lies not in the immediate realization of a unified network of laboratories, but in the
459 identification of design requirements for enabling infrastructures. In this perspective, the digital
460 platform is conceptualized as a boundary object supporting discoverability, coordination, and
461 early-stage interaction, as opposed to a mere substitute for organizational commitment or
462 governance.

463

464 By translating observed tensions and design challenges into platform functionalities, such as

465 structured visibility of competencies, tools for early collaboration, and support for cross-context
466 interaction, the platform aims to lower discovery and coordination costs while preserving
467 institutional diversity. This design-oriented interpretation sets the stage for the subsequent
468 discussion of platform architecture and future research directions.

469

470 **4.1 Consolidation and Launch of Lab Villages**

471

472 **4.1 From pilot experiences to infrastructural consolidation**

473

474 Following the exploratory and design-oriented phases described in Chapters 2 and 3, Cross-
475 Cutting Activity #2 (CC2) entered a phase focused on consolidating insights derived from pilot
476 experiences and translating them into shared infrastructural elements. Milestone 19 (M19) did not
477 mark the completion of a fully operational network, but rather the transition toward early-stage
478 implementation of selected organizational and digital components.

479

480 At this stage, pilot experiences conducted across different Spokes provided heterogeneous and
481 context-specific outcomes. While some initiatives contributed to clarifying governance
482 arrangements or engagement formats, others primarily generated methodological or conceptual
483 insights. Importantly, these experiences did not result in a uniform or standardized realization of
484 Lab Villages across the ecosystem. Instead, they highlighted persistent differences in institutional
485 readiness, sectoral focus, and organizational constraints.

486

487 In this sense, the contribution of the M19 phase lies less in the consolidation of physical structures
488 than in the progressive articulation of a shared infrastructural vision. This vision is oriented toward
489 enabling future coordination and interoperability, as opposed to merely certifying a homogeneous
490 and fully operational network.

491

492 **4.2 The digital platform as an enabling infrastructure**

493

494 Within this context, the Lab Village digital platform emerged as a central design response to the
495 fragmentation and discoverability challenges identified in the earlier phases. Beyond its
496 conception as a completed product or a fully deployed system, the platform is framed as an
497 enabling socio-technical infrastructure in early-stage development.

498

499 The responsibility for the platform's design and coordination was assigned to Spoke 3 (University
500 of Udine), acting in its role as CC2 leader. During the M19 phase, activities focused on three main
501 areas: the elicitation of functional requirements based on design-relevant dimensions identified in
502 Chapter 3; the selection of a software development partner through a public procurement process;
503 and the definition of an initial architectural framework emphasizing modularity and future
504 extensibility.

505

506 From a conceptual perspective, the platform is not intended to replace existing organizational
507 arrangements or governance mechanisms. Instead, it functions as a boundary object supporting
508 visibility, initial interaction, and coordination among heterogeneous actors. In line with research
509 on digital platforms and innovation ecosystems, its potential contribution depends on processes
510 of organizational adaptation and co-invention by participating institutions, instead of relying on
511 technological features alone (Bresnahan & Trajtenberg, 1995; Gawer, 2021).

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517 **4.3 Core platform functions**

518

519 The platform's design is oriented around a limited set of core functions, reflecting the exploratory
520 and enabling nature of the initiative.

521

522 These functions are consistent with the recent characterisation of digital platforms for knowledge
523 exchange proposed by Albats et al. (2025), which highlights information dissemination,
524 networking, and matchmaking as primary pillars for bridging the gap between academia and
525 industry.

526

527

528 **Figure 5.** Architectural framework of the Lab Village platform functions: from initial
529 matchmaking to collaborative co-creation.

530

531 First, as illustrated in Figure 5, the platform aims to support visibility and networking by providing
532 structured representations of laboratories, competencies, and research areas. This functionality
533 addresses information fragmentation and is intended to lower discovery costs for both academic
534 and industrial actors.

535

536 Second, the platform incorporates digital co-working features designed to facilitate early-stage
537 interaction and remote collaboration. These tools are conceived as complements to physical Lab
538 Village activities, supporting hybrid collaboration formats rather than substituting in-person
539 engagement.

540

541 Third, the platform is designed to host matchmaking mechanisms that assist users in identifying
542 potential collaborators based on expressed needs and available competencies. At this stage,
543 these mechanisms are conceptual and experimental, and their effectiveness has not yet been
544 empirically validated.

545

546

547 **4.4 Modular extensions and experimental components**

548

549 Beyond its core functionalities, the platform architecture allows for the integration of experimental
550 modules developed by individual Spokes. These modules are not presented as mature or fully
551 operational solutions, but as technological explorations aligned with the platform's enabling logic.

552

553 One such component is T-Cube (Tool for Competence Interaction), developed within Spoke 9
554 (SISSA). T-Cube explores the use of artificial intelligence and large language models to support
555 semantic mediation between industrial problem descriptions and academic competencies.
556 Instead of seeking to provide exhaustive matchmaking, the tool functions as an experimental
557 interface aimed at reducing linguistic and cognitive barriers in early-stage interaction (Scuola
558 Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati & University of Trieste, 2025).

559

560 Another exploratory module is the Online Lab Virtual Tool, developed by Spoke 1 (Free University
561 of Bozen-Bolzano). This initiative investigates the use of virtual and augmented reality to create
562 digital representations of laboratory environments. The primary objective is to enhance
563 preliminary understanding and accessibility of complex infrastructures, particularly for small and
564 medium-sized enterprises facing spatial or logistical constraints. The tool should be interpreted
565 as a complementary visualization resource not a as a substitute for physical access or hands-on
566 experimentation.

567

568 Together, these modules illustrate how the Lab Village platform is conceived as an evolving and
569 extensible infrastructure, open to experimentation and iterative refinement. Their integration
570 highlights the potential role of digital technologies as mediators in collaborative innovation
571 processes, while also underscoring the need for cautious interpretation of their impact in the
572 absence of sustained empirical use (Nambisan, 2017).

573

574

575 **4.5 Community-building as an Enabling Layer of the Lab Village Platform**

576

577 The critical analysis conducted in the previous phases of CC2 highlighted that the main barriers
578 to effective university–industry collaboration within the iNEST ecosystem were not primarily
579 infrastructural, but relational and organizational in nature. As discussed in Chapters 2 and 3,
580 building upon a context where collaboration across Spokes had historically been episodic and
581 weakly formalized, the project faced the challenge of transitioning from individual initiatives to
582 stable interaction mechanisms. These findings informed a key design decision: the Lab Village
583 Digital Platform was conceived not as a standalone technological artifact, but as a socio-technical
584 system requiring an explicit community-building layer to become operational and sustainable.

585

586 In this perspective, the activation and maintenance of a digital community is treated as an integral
587 component of the platform architecture. The underlying assumption is that visibility of laboratories
588 and competences is a necessary but insufficient condition for collaboration. Without facilitation,
589 shared practices, and recurring interaction formats, platforms risk remaining underutilized
590 repositories as opposed to evolving into functioning innovation ecosystems. This aligns with the
591 literature on digital platforms for innovation, which emphasizes the role of orchestration,
592 governance, and social engagement in reducing coordination and discovery costs among
593 heterogeneous actors (Gawer, 2021; Nambisan, 2017).

594

595 To operationalize this layer, a structured community-building process was designed to
596 accompany the technical development of the platform. This process focuses on defining
597 participation roles, interaction formats, and communication strategies aimed at fostering trust,
598 engagement, and gradual alignment between academic and industrial users. Rather than
599 targeting immediate industrial outputs, the community layer is intended to support early-stage

600 interactions, mutual understanding, and the emergence of collaboration opportunities over time.

601

602 From a design standpoint, the community-building activities are articulated through a set of
603 complementary artefacts that support both platform adoption and iterative refinement. These
604 include a methodological manual for the creation and management of the Lab Village community,
605 an editorial and activity calendar designed to stimulate continuous participation, and a structured
606 analysis of user experience addressing visual identity, communication clarity, and usability. In
607 addition, dedicated communication materials, such as a professional presentation for institutional
608 and industrial stakeholders and a series of short promotional videos, are conceived as boundary
609 objects to translate the platform's value proposition across different audiences.

610

611 Importantly, the community-building layer also functions as a feedback mechanism for platform
612 evolution. Insights derived from user interactions, communication performance, and usability
613 analysis are intended to inform subsequent iterations of the digital infrastructure, strengthening
614 the alignment between technological functionalities and actual collaboration practices. In this
615 sense, community-building is not treated as a dissemination activity, but as a core enabling
616 process for the emergence of a functioning Lab Village network.

617

618 While the community is still in its initial activation phase and does not yet allow for an ex post
619 evaluation of its impact on sustained university–industry collaboration, its integration into the CC2
620 design represents a deliberate response to the structural limitations identified in earlier phases.
621 This approach reinforces the interpretation of the Lab Village as a socio-technical boundary
622 infrastructure, where digital tools, organizational practices, and relational dynamics co-evolve to
623 support open innovation within a distributed regional ecosystem.

624

625

626 **5. Discussion and limitations**

627

628 **5.1 Interpreting CC2 beyond outcome-based evaluation**

629

630 The analysis presented in this paper should not be interpreted as an evaluation of finalized
631 outputs or measurable impacts. Instead, CC2 is examined as an early-stage infrastructural and
632 organizational process embedded within a complex, multi-institutional ecosystem. The value of
633 the activity lies primarily in its exploratory and design-oriented nature, as opposed to focusing on
634 immediate, in demonstrable performance outcomes.

635

636 The mapping (Chapter 2) and critical analysis (Chapter 3) highlight that the creation of strategic
637 university–industry joint laboratories cannot be reduced to the availability of physical spaces or
638 funding instruments. Rather, such initiatives are shaped by pre-existing institutional cultures,
639 governance arrangements, and relational capacities. In this sense, CC2 functioned as a
640 coordination mechanism aimed at making heterogeneity visible and actionable, not eliminating it.

641

642 This perspective aligns with innovation ecosystem literature that emphasizes processes of
643 alignment, learning, and negotiation over linear models of implementation (Gawer, 2021). The
644 Lab Village should therefore be interpreted not as a fixed organizational form, but as an evolving
645 configuration whose realization depends on sustained institutional engagement beyond the
646 project's initial phases.

647

648 **5.2 The platform as an infrastructural hypothesis**

649

650 A central contribution of CC2 is the conceptualization of the digital platform as an enabling
651 infrastructure instead of a self-contained solution. The platform is designed to lower discovery

652 and coordination costs by increasing the visibility of competencies, laboratories, and potential
653 collaboration opportunities across the ecosystem. However, at the time of analysis, its
654 functionality remains largely untested in real, long-term collaborative settings.

655

656 This distinction is critical. Digital platforms in innovation ecosystems do not automatically generate
657 collaboration; their effectiveness depends on complementary organizational practices, incentive
658 structures, and governance mechanisms (Bresnahan & Trajtenberg, 1995; Nambisan, 2017). The
659 Lab Village platform should therefore be understood as an infrastructural hypothesis: a designed
660 artifact whose potential value must be validated through sustained use, adaptation, and
661 institutional learning.

662

663 In this regard, CC2 explicitly acknowledges that the reduction of discovery costs through digital
664 visibility must be complemented by mechanisms capable of addressing relational and cognitive
665 barriers to collaboration. The design of the platform is therefore coupled with a community-
666 building layer aimed at fostering engagement, trust, and repeated interaction among academic
667 and industrial actors. This layer is intended to support the social activation of the infrastructure,
668 mitigating the risk that the platform remains an underutilized repository failing to evolve into a
669 functioning coordination space.

670

671 From this perspective, the platform's main contribution is not the automation of matchmaking or
672 collaboration, but the provision of a shared reference space capable of supporting interaction
673 among heterogeneous actors. Its success is contingent on future integration into universities' third
674 mission strategies and firms' innovation processes.

675

676

677 **5.3 Structural and methodological limitations**

678

679 Several limitations constrain the interpretation of the findings presented in this study.

680

681 First, the empirical basis is limited to internal project documentation, qualitative mapping, and
682 early-stage pilot experiences. No longitudinal data on collaboration outcomes, economic impact,
683 or knowledge transfer effectiveness are available at this stage. As a result, claims regarding
684 performance, scalability, or sustainability would be premature.

685

686 Second, while the integration of a community-building process represents a deliberate response
687 to the relational gaps identified in earlier phases, this component is still in its initial activation
688 stage. Consequently, its effects on sustained collaboration, platform adoption, and ecosystem
689 dynamics cannot yet be empirically assessed and remain an important avenue for future
690 evaluation.

691

692 Third, the heterogeneity of the Spokes, while analytically valuable, limits the comparability of
693 experiences. Differences in size, disciplinary focus, administrative capacity, and regional
694 industrial structure significantly influence the feasibility and form of Lab Village initiatives. The
695 scoring and classification methods introduced in M18 served primarily as heuristic tools to guide
696 coordination, rather than as rigorous evaluative instruments.

697

698 Fourth, the study is embedded within a PNRR-funded framework, which introduces specific
699 temporal constraints and incentive structures. The short time horizon of milestones and
700 deliverables may favor visible infrastructural outputs over the slower processes of trust-building
701 and organizational change that university–industry collaboration typically requires.

702

703

704

705 **5.4 Implications for policy and future research**

706

707 Despite these limitations, the CC2 experience offers relevant insights for policymakers and
708 researchers interested in collaborative research infrastructures. One key implication is that large-
709 scale funding programs should account for the organizational and relational work required to
710 make joint laboratories operational, rather than assuming that financial investment alone will
711 generate collaboration.

712

713 The transition from funded pilot phases to self-sustaining innovation networks remains a critical
714 challenge for PNRR-funded initiatives. As highlighted by Compagnucci et al. (2025), the evolution
715 of these ecosystems depends on their ability to institutionalize knowledge transfer practices. The
716 digital and organizational framework of the Lab Village proposed in this study directly addresses
717 this need, providing the 'relational infrastructure' necessary for the long-term viability of the
718 ecosystem.

719

720 For future research, the Lab Village initiative provides a fertile ground for longitudinal studies
721 examining how digital platforms, governance models, and institutional incentives interact over
722 time. Empirical investigation should focus on whether and how such infrastructures contribute to
723 sustained partnerships, knowledge co-creation, and regional innovation dynamics once funding
724 phases end.

725

726 Finally, the strategic value of initiatives like CC2 may lie less in immediate outputs and more in
727 their capacity to produce shared languages, design principles, and coordination mechanisms. In
728 this perspective, the future evolution of iNEST points toward the institutionalization of a "Network
729 of Lab Villages", comprising both physical and virtual spaces where joint university-industry
730 laboratories coexist and interact. As officially outlined by the Rector of the University of Udine
731 (who also served as coordinator of the CC2 activities) during the inauguration of the Academic
732 Year, this network is intended to be a stable model for applied research and territorial
733 engagement, supported by the digital platform as its enabling infrastructure. This vision
734 underscores the transition from a project-based logic to a permanent regional innovation asset.

735

736 **6. Conclusions**

737

738 This paper has examined the CC2 activity within the iNEST ecosystem as a process of
739 conceptualization, mapping, and infrastructural design aimed at enabling strategic university-
740 industry collaboration through the Lab Village model. Rather than reporting consolidated
741 outcomes, the study documents an early-stage attempt to structure heterogeneous collaborative
742 practices into a coherent and scalable framework.

743

744 The analysis shows that the primary challenge in creating joint strategic laboratories does not lie
745 in the availability of physical infrastructures, which are often already present, but in the absence
746 of shared organizational models, governance mechanisms, and coordination tools. CC2
747 addressed this challenge by introducing a common conceptual language, a set of design
748 principles, and a digital platform conceived as an enabling infrastructure to support visibility,
749 matchmaking, and collaboration across institutional boundaries.

750

751 A key contribution of this work is the reframing of the Lab Village not as a predefined
752 organizational solution, but as an evolving socio-technical configuration. Its effectiveness
753 depends on long-term institutional commitment, relational capabilities, and the integration of
754 digital tools into universities' third mission strategies and firms' innovation processes.

755

756 While the empirical evidence remains preliminary, the CC2 experience provides insights into the
757 organizational conditions required to move from episodic university-industry interactions toward

758 more strategic and sustained forms of co-creation. In this sense, the paper contributes to the
759 literature on innovation ecosystems by highlighting the importance of design-oriented
760 coordination mechanisms as prerequisites for collaborative research infrastructures, particularly
761 in fragmented regional contexts.

762

763 Overall, the CC2 experience suggests that the creation of strategic university–industry laboratory
764 networks depends less on the availability of shared infrastructures alone and more on the co-
765 evolution of digital platforms, organizational practices, and community-building mechanisms
766 capable of activating and sustaining collaboration over time.

767

768

769

Author Contributions

770

771 Conceptualization, A.B., A.M., M.C. G.M.; methodology, A.B.; formal analysis, A.B.; investigation,
772 A.B.; resources, A.B.; data curation, A.B.; writing original draft preparation, A.B.; writing review
773 and editing, A.B.; visualization, A.B.; supervision, M.C. A.M.; project administration, M.C., G.M.
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Data Availability Statement

793 The data supporting the conclusions of this article are available on Zenodo, at the following:

794 https://zenodo.org/communities/inest_cc2

795

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800

801

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

- AI – Artificial Intelligence
- AR – Augmented Reality
- CC – Cross-Cutting Activity
- CC2 – Cross-Cutting Activity #2
- DCC2.1 – Deliverable of Cross-Cutting Activity #2, version 1
- DCC2.2 – Deliverable of Cross-Cutting Activity #2, version 2
- ERA – European Research Area
- EU – European Union
- iNEST – Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem
- IUAV – Università luav di Venezia
- M17 – Milestone 17
- M18 – Milestone 18
- M19 – Milestone 19
- M20 – Milestone 20
- MUR – Ministry of Universities and Research (Italy)
- PNRR – Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan)
- SISSA – Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati
- SMEs – Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
- T-Cube – Tool for Competence Interaction
- VR – Virtual Reality

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

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